

Therapeutic drug monitoring for optimizing ustekinumab therapy in Iraqi patients with psoriasis: A real-world study

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Abstract

Psoriasis is a complex autoimmune disorder characterized by skin inflammation with keratinocyte proliferation, and 85% of cases present as plaque-type psoriasis. Biologics such as ustekinumab (UST) are highly successful therapies for psoriasis. To achieve maximum clinical efficacy while minimizing undesirable effects, therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) for biologics has emerged. This study aims to measure the UST trough level (TL) and anti-drug antibodies (ADAs) and to evaluate clinical response in Iraqi patients with moderate-to-severe psoriasis in order to make appropriate recommendations for modifying therapy. This cross-sectional study enrolled 75 patients, divided into two groups: Group 1, patients who achieved the UST target TL ($\geq 0.6 \mu\text{g/mL}$); and Group 2, patients who did not achieve the UST target TL ($< 0.6 \mu\text{g/mL}$). Significant differences were found in Psoriasis Area and Severity Index scores ($P = 0.001$) and body surface area involvement ($P = 0.003$), with Group 1 demonstrating lower values, indicating lower disease severity. No significant difference in ADA concentration was found between groups, and only two patients tested positive in Group 2. Based on the UST TL, ADAs, and clinical response, recommendations included dose escalation or shortening of the dosing interval for 29 patients, continuation of therapy for 34 patients, or switching to an alternative biologic agent for 12 patients. These findings reinforce the value of TDM in guiding personalized treatment decisions and highlight the clinical utility of integrating TL and ADA assessments into real-world practice.

Keywords

anti-drug antibodies, psoriasis, therapeutic drug monitoring, trough level, ustekinumab

Introduction

Psoriasis is a complex, immune-mediated disorder marked by skin inflammation and hyperproliferation of epidermal keratinocytes (Kanda 2021). It has a global prevalence estimated at 1–3% (Papp et al. 2021). Psoriasis affects both sexes equally, and 75% of cases are diagnosed before the age of 40 (Dairov et al. 2024). Environmental

factors and genetic predisposition are the major determinants of psoriasis etiology (Hernandez-Nicols et al. 2024). Both can elicit innate and adaptive immune responses, leading to the generation of pro-inflammatory cytokines that support the survival and growth of T-helper 1 (Th1) and T-helper 17 (Th17) cells. Th1 cells produce interferon gamma (IFN- γ) and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), while Th17 cells release interleukin (IL)-17, IL-22, and

TNF- α , leading to keratinocyte activation and proliferation, thereby sustaining chronic skin inflammation (Armstrong and Read 2020). Psoriasis can present in many phenotypes; however, plaque psoriasis accounts for 85% of cases, marked by sharply defined, erythematous, scaly areas on the scalp, trunk, gluteal folds, knees, and elbows (Rendon and Schakel 2019).

Current therapeutic options, including topical medications, phototherapy, and immune modulators, may provide symptomatic relief and improve quality of life (Abdulridha et al. 2020), but are associated with challenges of treatment resistance and adverse effects (Lee and Kim 2023). When traditional treatments fail, biologics, such as monoclonal antibodies and receptor fusion proteins, have been introduced to achieve long-term remission in moderate-to-severe psoriasis (Palakornkitti et al. 2021). Ustekinumab (UST) is a fully human immunoglobulin 1 (IgG1) kappa (κ) monoclonal antibody that targets the p40 subunit of cytokines IL-12 and IL-23 (Klimko et al. 2024). UST has excellent specificity and affinity for the p40 subunit, thereby preventing IL-12 and IL-23 from engaging T cell receptor complexes involved in psoriasis pathogenesis. This mechanism inhibits downstream inflammatory signaling and keratinocyte proliferation, leading to a considerable decrease in skin lesions and disease severity (Wcisło-Dziadecka et al. 2019).

Biologics are highly successful therapies for psoriasis, although they are typically recommended using a one-dose-fits-all strategy. This traditional strategy can lead to inadequate dosing or overdose, potentially resulting in an unsatisfactory therapeutic response or unnecessarily high drug exposure (Eylenbosch et al. 2024). Another downside of biologics is that, as proteins, they can generate so-called anti-drug antibodies (ADAs) (Al-Jalehawi and Mohammad 2024). In some patients, ADAs may decrease drug levels and diminish clinical efficacy, while in others, they have been associated with adverse effects such as infusion reactions (Hassaan et al. 2023). Despite their high efficacy, biologics are not effective for everyone with psoriasis (primary failure). Furthermore, some responders experience secondary failure over time, which has been associated with low serum levels and the formation of ADAs (Elberdín et al. 2022). Three mechanisms may be the cause of drug failure. Mechanistic failure occurs when a patient does not respond to appropriate medication. Inflammatory mediators most likely cause this type of failure, which the drug does not inhibit, promoting the disease process. Non-immune-mediated pharmacokinetic failure occurs when a patient's TL of a medication is lower than required for therapy and no neutralizing ADAs exist. Immune-mediated pharmacokinetic failure occurs when the immune system produces ADAs that inhibit the medication, leading to low or unmeasurable TL and, therefore, treatment failure (Saleh et al. 2024; Saleh et al. 2025). For these reasons, therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) for biologics is an emerging clinical practice aimed at achieving

maximum clinical efficacy while minimizing undesirable effects (Liau and Oon 2019). It involves assessing drug concentrations in blood, serum, or other biological fluids to inform prescribing and adjust dosing (Almohammed et al. 2021).

TDM may be reactive or proactive. Non-responder patients undergo reactive TDM, which involves testing for serum drug levels and ADAs to identify the causes of primary treatment failure. Proactive TDM measures serum drug levels and ADAs in responder patients to optimize therapy, aiming to reduce future flares and loss of response (LOR) and to maximize pharmacologic efficacy (Shmais et al. 2022). Serum UST level is not routinely monitored in clinical practice, and there is limited evidence for TDM with this medication. In the case of psoriasis, the basic fundamental requirements for the therapeutic range and target drug level remain uncertain (Tsakok et al. 2019). This study aims to measure UST trough level, assess the development of ADAs, and evaluate response in Iraqi patients with moderate-to-severe psoriasis to make appropriate recommendations for modifying UST treatment and to establish the clinical value of TDM in routine practice.

Patients, materials, and methods

Study population and design

A cross-sectional study was conducted from March–August 2025 at the Center of Dermatology and Venereology, Baghdad Teaching Hospital, Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq. The study enrolled 75 patients; each was supervised by a specialist dermatologist and managed in accordance with the American Academy of Dermatology guidelines (Menter et al. 2019). All patients received subcutaneous UST 90 mg at weeks 0 and 4 (induction dose), then every 12 weeks thereafter (maintenance dose). Detailed family, medical, surgical, and smoking histories were collected, along with medical records of baseline and last Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) and body surface area (BSA) involvement. Clinical response was evaluated using the PASI score, where an optimal response was defined as PASI ≤ 3 , while values >3 indicated a suboptimal response (Elberdín et al. 2022). Age, body mass index (BMI), disease duration, and UST treatment duration of all patients were recorded.

Grouping of study participants

Patients were allocated into two groups according to target TL achievement (Elberdín et al. 2022):

- Group 1: Includes patients who achieved the UST target TL (≥ 0.6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$).
- Group 2: Includes patients who did not achieve the UST target TL (< 0.6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria

1. Patients diagnosed with moderate-to-severe plaque-type psoriasis according to the PASI score (Ko et al. 2016).
2. Age over 18 years.
3. Adherent patients on regular maintenance UST doses for at least 6 months according to patient medical records.

Exclusion criteria

1. Patients with other accompanying immune diseases.
2. Patients using anti-inflammatory medication in addition to UST.
3. Patients with psoriasis types other than plaque psoriasis or concomitant skin disease.
4. Patients with insufficient clinical records or who refused informed consent were also excluded.

Ethical approval

The study was approved by the Scientific and Ethical Committee at the College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad (approval name: REC062444H, date 20 October 2024). Before sample collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Blood samples and data collection

Each participant provided 5 milliliters of venous blood just before the next UST dose to measure serum TL. The collected blood samples were centrifuged at 4,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The serum was then isolated and stored at -80°C for additional analysis. Serum UST concentration was measured using an indirect enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kit (FineTest, Cat. No. EH5320, China) following the manufacturer's protocol. Free ADAs against UST were measured using a sandwich ELISA kit (IDKmonitor, Cat. No. K9666, Germany).

Statistical analysis

The Shapiro–Wilk test was employed to assess the normality of variables. Normal distributions were expressed as mean and standard deviation (SD), while non-normal distributions were expressed as median and interquartile range (IQR). An independent t-test was used to compare variables that were normally distributed. If data did not follow normality, the Mann–Whitney U test was employed. The chi-square test was used to compare cat-

egorical variables. Binary logistic regression analysis was utilized to examine the correlation between TL achievement and other factors. SPSS 27 (Chicago, USA) was used for the analysis, with statistical significance identified by a p-value <0.05 .

Results

The demographic and disease characteristics of the patients are presented in Table 1. More than two-thirds of the sample were males, while the remaining participants were females (69.33% and 30.67%, respectively). The participants had an average age of 38.88 ± 13.17 years and a BMI of 29.18 ± 4.60 kg/m². The median duration of psoriasis and median UST therapy were 12 years and 19 months, respectively. In terms of clinical background, 37.7% of patients had a family history of psoriasis, 29.3% had undergone surgical procedures, and 22.7% had medical comorbidities. Smoking was reported by 12% of the participants. Patients with moderate-to-severe disease activity at enrollment were ineligible for UST therapy, as evidenced by baseline PASI and BSA median values of 19 and 31, respectively.

Table 1. Demographic data of the patients.

Variable	Results
(Sex) Female [n (%)]	23 (30.67%)
Male [n (%)]	52 (69.33%)
Age (years) [mean \pm SD]	38.88 ± 13.17
BMI (kg/m ²) [mean \pm SD]	29.18 ± 4.60
Disease duration (years) [median (IQR)]	[12.00 (7.50–20.00)]
Ustekinumab treatment duration (months) [median (IQR)]	[19.00 (10.00–22.00)]
Family history of psoriasis[n (%)]	[28 (37.7%)]
Surgical history [n (%)]	[22 (29.3%)]
Medical history [n (%)]	[17 (22.7%)]
Smoking history[n (%)]	[9 (12.0%)]
PASI score	Baseline [19.00 (13.00–28.00)]
[median (IQR)]	Last [2.00 (1.00–4.10)]
BSA (m ²)	Baseline [34.00 (25.00–45.00)]
[median (IQR)]	Last [2.00 (1.00–9.50)]

BMI: body mass index; BSA: body surface area; IQR: interquartile range; PASI: Psoriasis Area and Severity Index; SD: standard deviation.

A comparison of demographic and disease characteristics between patients who achieved therapeutic levels of UST (Group 1) and those who did not (Group 2) is illustrated in Table 2. No significant differences in sex distribution, age, BMI, disease duration, or treatment duration were observed ($P > 0.05$ for all). Baseline PASI and BSA scores were similar; however, at the last follow-up visit, Group 1 demonstrated significantly lower PASI scores ($P = 0.001$) and significantly lower BSA involvement ($P = 0.003$).

Table 2. Difference between psoriasis patients who achieved TL (Group 1) and patients who did not achieve TL (Group 2) according to patients' demographics and disease characteristics.

Variable	Study groups		P-value	
	Group 1 (TL \geq 0.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) (N = 44)	Group 2 (TL < 0.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) (N = 31)		
Sex (a): Female [n (%)]	14 (31.82%)	9 (29.03%)	0.797	
Male [n (%)]	30 (68.18%)	22 (70.97%)		
Age(year) [mean \pm SD] (b)	[38.11 \pm 13.73]	[39.96 \pm 12.46]	0.623	
BMI (kg/m ²) [mean \pm SD] (b)	[28.72 \pm 5.26]	[29.83 \pm 3.43]	0.347	
Disease duration (years) [median (IQR)] (c)	[10.5 (6.00–19.50)]	[12.00 (10.00–20.00)]	0.377	
Ustekinumab treatment duration (months) [median (IQR)] (c)	[19 (10.00–23.50)]	[16 (7.00–22.00)]	0.367	
PASI score (b)	Baseline	21.78 \pm 10.73	21.04 \pm 10.35	0.766
	Last	2.19 \pm 1.78	4.35 \pm 2.91	0.001*
BSA (m ²) (b)	Baseline	35.14 \pm 14.39	36.42 \pm 18.22	0.764
	Last	3.50 \pm 2.83	6.58 \pm 4.07	0.003*

BMI: body mass index; BSA: body surface area; IQR: interquartile range; PASI: Psoriasis Area and Severity Index; TL: trough level; (*) significant difference ($P < 0.01$); (a) chi-square test; (b) two-sample *t*-test; (c) Mann–Whitney U-test.

Table 3 presents a comparison of TL and ADAs of UST between the study groups. A highly significant difference in the mean UST TL was observed between groups, with a higher drug concentration in Group 1 ($P = 0.001$). In contrast, there was no statistically significant difference in ADA concentrations between the two groups ($P = 0.5$).

Table 3. Difference between psoriasis patients who achieved TL (Group 1) and patients who did not achieve TL (Group 2) according to ustekinumab TL and ADA.

Variable	Group 1 TL \geq 0.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Group 2 TL< 0.6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	P-value
TL ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) [mean \pm SD]	1.06 \pm 0.22	0.52 \pm 0.06	0.001*
ADA (AU/ml) [mean \pm SD]	7.69 \pm 2.57	8.17 \pm 2.75	0.451

ADA: anti-drug antibody; TL: trough level. A two-sample *t*-test was used; (*) highly significant difference ($P < 0.01$).

The association between baseline demographic and clinical characteristics and the achievement of the target TL was evaluated using univariate logistic regression analysis. None of the investigated baseline variables, including sex, age, duration of disease, smoking history, PASI score, and BSA, showed a discernible association with target TL achievement. While not statistically significant, one variable showed a trend toward association. Family history of psoriasis exhibited the strongest tendency, suggesting that patients with a family history were approximately

Table 4. Target TL achievement prediction by univariate analysis.

Variable	Univariate analysis ^(a)	
	OR (95% CI)	P-value
Sex	0.877 (0.322–2.388)	0.797
Baseline age (years)	0.989 (0.955–1.025)	0.546
Baseline duration of the disease (years)	0.976 (0.924–1.030)	0.377
Family history of psoriasis	2.396 (0.882–6.510)	0.087
Smoking history	0.865 (0.213–3.521)	0.840
Baseline PASI score	1.006 (0.968–1.045)	0.763
Baseline BSA (m ²)	1.000 (0.979–1.021)	0.989

BSA: body surface area; PASI: Psoriasis Area and Severity Index; CI: confidence interval; OR: odds ratio; TL: trough level. (a) Binary logistic regression was used.

2.4 times more likely to achieve the target outcome (OR: 2.396, 95% CI: 0.882–6.510, $P = 0.087$). These findings indicate that none of the baseline factors evaluated is a single, strong, independent predictor of treatment success.

Table 5 presents the classification of psoriasis patients according to their UST TL, ADA status, and clinical response, along with the corresponding therapeutic recommendations (Shubow et al. 2025). Based on these classifications, treatment recommendations varied across subgroups. They included dose escalation or shortening of the dosing interval (29 patients), continuation of therapy (34 patients), or switching to an alternative biologic agent (12 patients).

Table 5. Classification of patients and recommendations based on TL, ADA, and disease activity.

Patients did not achieve the target TL [31 patients (41.33%)]		Patients achieved the target TL [44 patients (58.66%)]	
[16 patients] With optimal response	[15 patients] with suboptimal response		[34 patients] With optimal response
	[13 patients] with negative ADA (non-immune pharmacokinetic failure)	[2 patients] with high positive ADA (immune pharmacokinetic failure)	[10 patients] with suboptimal response
Recommendations			
Escalate therapy or shorten dosing interval	Escalate therapy or shorten dosing interval	Switch therapy	Continue therapy
			Mechanistic treatment failure
			Switch therapy

ADA: anti-drug antibody; TL: trough level.

Discussion

The current study was conducted to evaluate the feasibility and relevance of TDM in Iraqi patients with moderate-to-severe chronic plaque psoriasis. Based on an extensive literature review, it is the first clinical study in Iraq to assess the TL and ADAs of UST in psoriasis patients.

The overall clinical response to UST was excellent; however, some variance was observed between Group 1 ($n = 44$) and Group 2 ($n = 31$), grouped according to the achievement of the UST target TL, a key rationale for TDM (Table 2). Critically, despite non-comparable baseline disease severity, patients in Group 1 demonstrated a significantly better clinical response than those in Group 2 after treatment initiation, as evidenced by a lower mean final PASI score ($P = 0.001$). This finding underscores the importance of maintaining adequate drug exposure to achieve better medication efficacy. A significant concentration–response relationship was detected, with higher UST concentrations associated with superior clinical responses. Therefore, monitoring drug levels could help identify individuals who may benefit from UST dose modifications (Van den Berghe et al. 2020). This finding is reinforced by the significantly lower BSA involvement in Group 1 after treatment ($P = 0.003$). The two groups were statistically similar across key demographic and disease characteristics, including age, BMI, disease duration, and UST treatment duration ($P > 0.05$ for all).

Biological therapy is typically prescribed to achieve complete remission; however, suboptimal response in psoriasis remains a problem. An inadequate response may be attributed to patient variability in serum drug concentrations, which could be influenced by treatment adherence, BMI, and ADAs. Therefore, TDM is gaining attention for its ability to direct patient doses in a timely and adaptable manner, achieving optimal response and lower clinical costs (Pan et al. 2020). In the current study, patient adherence was confirmed through review of medical records, which verified that patients were adherent to their UST dosing regimen, with documented administration dates aligning with the recommended dosing interval. The results in Table 3 revealed a non-significant difference in ADAs ($P > 0.05$), with only 2 patients (2.6%) testing positive in Group 2, supporting that immunogenicity may not have a substantial impact on serum levels, as also reported in previous studies (Tsakok et al. 2019; Van den Berghe et al. 2020).

Factors predicting achievement of the target TL of UST were investigated among baseline demographic and clinical variables (Table 4), but none were significant. TL achievement was shown to be minimally influenced by sex and records obtained before UST therapy initiation (age, disease duration, smoking history, PASI, and BSA), and all demonstrated odds ratios close to unity. These findings reflect a relatively homogeneous patient cohort and a sustained UST pharmacokinetic profile. Previous studies usually tested these variables for predicting treatment response rather than serum drug concentration (Schwarz et

al. 2021; Youn et al. 2021). The only variable showing a borderline trend was family history of psoriasis ($P = 0.087$), which may indicate a potential genetic influence but did not reach statistical significance and should be interpreted with caution. The role of genetic factors remains underexplored. One study investigated the HLA-C06 genotype as a pharmacogenetic marker for UST responsiveness in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). However, no association was detected, indicating that this specific genetic marker may not influence UST serum concentrations in IBD (Corcoran et al. 2025). Overall, the lack of significant predictors highlights the complexity of determining which patients are most likely to reach the target TL.

The classification of patient samples (75 patients) based on TL, ADAs, and clinical response provided important insights into the mechanisms underlying treatment success or failure in psoriasis (Table 5). In the current study, 44 patients (Group 1) achieved the target TL for UST (58.66%). The majority of this group (34/44) achieved optimal clinical response ($PASI \leq 3$), confirming the importance of maintaining adequate drug exposure for therapeutic success. However, 10 patients showed suboptimal clinical improvement ($PASI > 3$), indicating mechanistic failure, where adequate pharmacokinetics are present but the drug is no longer effective in controlling the disease pathway. Mechanistic failures could arise from individual patient variability, such as differences in immune response or genetic factors (Bubna and Viplav 2024). For these individuals, switching therapy rather than dose adjustment is the most appropriate clinical decision (Shubow et al. 2025).

Target TL was not achieved by 31 patients (41.33%) despite ongoing biologic therapy (Group 2). More than half of them (16/31) demonstrated an optimal clinical response, suggesting that some individuals may benefit from a lower target TL of UST (Wang et al. 2022). In another study using UST for Crohn's disease, some patients maintained adequate disease control despite subtherapeutic drug levels (Afif et al. 2022). However, dose escalation or shortening the dosing interval is generally recommended for such patients, as they may be more prone to secondary loss of response (Shubow et al. 2025). Overall, UST has an excellent safety profile with few adverse effects observed, making it a feasible choice for dose adjustment (Alorfi et al. 2023).

Suboptimal clinical response was observed in others (13/31) who tested negative for ADAs, indicating non-immune-mediated pharmacokinetic failure. These patients may experience altered drug distribution or metabolism, driven by factors such as high BMI, longer disease duration, and prior tumor necrosis factor inhibitor use, which influence the patient's response to UST (Xu et al. 2021). Dose escalation or interval shortening is a rational strategy to restore the therapeutic exposure required for this group, except for patients who tested positive for ADAs (2/31) and who undergo immune-mediated pharmacokinetic failure, for whom switching to a biologic, preferably with lower immunogenicity or a different mechanism of action, is appropriate (Shubow et al. 2025).

Limitations

This study has some limitations that need to be addressed. It is possible that the small sample size affected the statistical power and the generalizability of the results. The results of TL and ADAs were delayed because patient samples were collected and stored for nearly 5 months before laboratory analysis. Consequently, the lag time between sampling and availability of results led to delayed treatment recommendations for clinicians and patients. Finally, patients were recruited from a single center, which may have introduced selection bias and limited external validity. Larger, multicenter studies with longer follow-up and more diverse patient populations are required to validate these findings and better understand the role of therapeutic drug monitoring in UST-treated psoriasis.

Conclusion

Overall, the findings of the current study suggest that TDM has strong potential to guide individualized treatment decisions in patients with moderate-to-severe psoriasis. Clinicians would benefit from distinguishing among the variable mechanisms of inadequate response (non-immune-mediated pharmacokinetic, immune-mediated, and mechanistic failure) to tailor management strategies and achieve an optimal response. The stratified recommendations provided in this study – dose escalation or interval shortening, continuation of therapy, or therapy switching – are consistent with current precision medicine approaches and demonstrate the therapeutic value of incorporating TL and ADA assessments into real-world practice.

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tients who participated in this study for their cooperation and willingness to contribute to the research.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The study was approved by the Scientific and Ethical Committee at the College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad (approval name: REC062444H, date 20/10/2024).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

The author's contributions are as follows: study conception and design, second author; data collection, first and third authors; draft manuscript preparation, first and second authors. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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